

2017 Usage Report for the IPCC DDC

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1. Summary

This report provides details of how the DDC web site, ipcc-data.org, was used in the 12 months from January 1st 2017 to December 31st 2017. The information presented here is generated using the Google Analytics service; providing a range of different statistics that cover both temporal and spatial trends. Only sessions which persist for longer than 10 seconds have been used in this analysis for consistency with the previous usage reports for TGICA. The Google Analytics statistics have also been filtered to remove robotic and other automated behaviour.

DDC access statistics for 2017 show a fall of about 4% compared to 2016. The Home page remains the most commonly viewed page on the DDC. Of note is the rise in the number of sessions based in Brazil which rose from 813 in 2016 to 1180 in 2017, an increase of 45%.

2. Evolution of User Sessions

The number of DDC page views recorded in 2017 is lower than the number of page views received in the previous year, a fall of about 4% from 182180 views in 2016 to 175088 views in 2017. Nevertheless the DDC continues to regularly receive over 2500 page views per week. A clear feature of both the 2016 and 2017 time series is a drop-off in session numbers during the Christmas holiday season (week index 0, 51). 2017 can be characterised by the increase in page views during October (week index 40, 41, 42) when compared to the same period in previous years. The sudden drop in usage in mid-November (week index 46) coincides with a short period where the DDC was offline for two days on the 21st and 22nd of November following a power surge at the STFC JASMIN facility which hosts the website.

Weekly user page views (longer than 10s) for the last five years are shown in figure 2 and provide a context for the two years of page view statistics shown in figure 1.

Figure1: Time series of weekly DDC page views for sessions with duration longer than 10s. The time axis is shown in weeks from January 1st. Two time series are shown: red for the period from January 1st 2017 to December 30th 2017 and blue for the previous 12 months.

Figure 2: Weekly page views (longer than 10s) for the five years from January 2013 to December 2017 inclusive.

3. Access Patterns by Page on the DDC

The IPCC-DDC home page remains the most commonly viewed page on the DDC, receiving 13% of page views in 2017 (figure 3). Other popular pages are those that explain some of the basic science behind climate change such as: Projected emissions and concentrations of carbon dioxide; Understanding the observational record; An Introduction to Global Climate Models (GCMs). It is clear that users are interested in using the DDC to access GCM data and information about the IPCC 5th Assessment Report (AR5).

The access pattern of pages across the IPCC-DDC is very similar to the distribution recorded in the March 2017 usage report.

Most users arriving at the DDC do so via the Home page, as previously reported to. It is helpful to know that users tend to arrive on the home page because this is where we provide information about the purpose of the site and an overview of the content that we provide. Most users visiting the guidance pages navigate there from another page on the DDC, this fits with the behaviour of a person who, having found some interesting data, decides to use our guidance documents to learn how to use it.

Again it is worth reiterating the importance of popular entry pages such as “What is a GCM?” and “CO2” as places where additional contextual information about the DDC can be placed. This is especially important to keep in mind if we move to a more modular site design in the future.

Distribution of page views across the DDC

Figure 3: Access distribution across the various pages of the IPCC-DDC that were visited during 2017.

Page on the DDC	URL	Number of unique Views	%
Home	www.ipcc-data.org/index.html	22274	12.72
CO2	www.ipcc-data.org/observ/ddc_co2.html	10588	6.05
Observations	www.ipcc-data.org/observ/index.html	10338	5.90
AR5 GCM data	www.ipcc-data.org/sim/gcm_monthly/AR5/index.html	8436	4.82
Simulations	www.ipcc-data.org/sim/index.html	7831	4.47
Climate Model Output	www.ipcc-data.org/sim/gcm_monthly/index.html	5931	3.39
Scenario Process for AR5: RCPs	sedac.ipcc-data.org/ddc/ar5_scenario_process/RCPs.html	5405	3.09
What is a GCM?	www.ipcc-data.org/guidelines/pages/gcm_guide.html	5235	2.99
AR4 GCM data	www.ipcc-data.org/sim/gcm_monthly/SRES_AR4/index.html	4972	2.84
Guidance	www.ipcc-data.org/guidelines/index.html	3940	2.25
AR4 Observations	www.ipcc-data.org/observ/clim/ar4_global.html	3845	2.20
Regional Scatter Plots	www.ipcc-data.org/syn/tar_scatter/index.html	3721	2.13
AR5 Reference Snapshot	www.ipcc-data.org/sim/gcm_monthly/AR5/Reference-Archive.html	3595	2.05
Scenario Process for AR5	sedac.ipcc-data.org/ddc/ar5_scenario_process/index.html	3298	1.88

Table 1: The same information as in the pie chart in figure 3 but with the page URLs shown.

Access distribution across the DDC

Figure 4: The overall number of unique views per page (blue) and the number of entrances per page (red) during 2017. Users tend to arrive at pages where the number of entrances are about equal to the number of page views and navigate to pages where the number of entrances are much less than the number of page views.

4. Geographical Distribution of Engagement with the DDC

Geographical Distribution of Sessions by Continent

Figure 5

re 5: The geographical distribution of DDC sessions (duration > 10s) by continent for 2017.

Geographical Distribution of Sessions by Country

Figure 6

re 6: The geographical distribution of DDC user sessions (duration > 10s) by country for 2017.

Sessions initiated by users in Europe, Asia and North America account for 84% of DDC activity (figure 5) however approximately half of the DDC sessions are initiated by users in just seven countries. Nevertheless the DDC plays an increasingly important role in many countries in spite of their relatively small number of page views.

Figure 6, which names the top 17 countries that make use of the DDC, is a useful way to showcase those countries that access the DDC most frequently. Users in the top 7 countries account for 51% of all sessions: USA 20%, UK 8%, India 6%, China 6%, Canada 4% and Germany 4% and Brazil 3%. “other” countries not listed here account for 29% of user sessions. 2017 has seen a rise in the number of sessions based in Brazil which rose from 813 in 2016 to 1180 in 2017, an increase of 45%. A full breakdown by country of the DDC user sessions is shown in appendix A.

5. Browser Statistics

The IPCC-DDC site is available and accessible to all the major internet browsers and operating systems. English is the most used language setting, accounting for 64% of sessions (figure 7). Chrome is the most popular browser, accounting for 63% of sessions and Windows is the most popular operating system, accounting for 75% of sessions (figure 8).

Distribution of Sessions by Language Setting

Figure 7: Language settings for DDC user sessions during 2017.

Sessions by Browser

Sessions by OS

Figure 8: Browser and technology characteristics of DDC user sessions with information about Browsers, Operating Systems that are used to access the DDC during 2017.

Appendix

A full breakdown, by country, of the DDC user sessions during 2017.

Country	Sessions	Country	Sessions	Country	Sessions
United States	7329	Hong Kong	208	Costa Rica	44
United Kingdom	2795	Austria	182	Cameroon	48
India	2197	Chile	174	Madagascar	46
China	2221	Argentina	171	Fiji	33
Canada	1640	New Zealand	167	Cambodia	42
Germany	1513	Finland	158	Bulgaria	42
Brazil	1180	Greece	174	Israel	41
Australia	878	Peru	158	Guatemala	33
Spain	763	Bangladesh	150	Senegal	45
France	759	Kenya	142	Brunei	37
Iran	1128	Singapore	131	Zimbabwe	35
Italy	751	Egypt	133	United Arab Emirates	31
Japan	788	Poland	134	Lebanon	34
Netherlands	659	Nigeria	119	Benin	38
Russia	611	Vietnam	178	Tunisia	48
Sweden	518	Nepal	124	Rwanda	39
South Korea	500	(not set)	117	Jordan	27
Mexico	420	Ireland	112	Kazakhstan	25
Indonesia	447	Sri Lanka	103	Croatia	24
Thailand	496	Morocco	135	Mongolia	29
Switzerland	344	Ecuador	100	Serbia	21
Taiwan	440	Saudi Arabia	83	Jamaica	23
South Africa	307	Algeria	88	Slovenia	21
Ethiopia	279	Czechia	78	Botswana	25
Turkey	278	Bolivia	70	Côte d'Ivoire	23
Denmark	262	Hungary	56	Lithuania	22
Pakistan	295	Ghana	58	Estonia	22
Malaysia	330	Romania	54	Malawi	18
Colombia	268	Iraq	71	Qatar	26
Philippines	223	Ukraine	48	Honduras	21
Belgium	227	Venezuela	61	Myanmar (Burma)	20
Portugal	237	Tanzania	50	Slovakia	25
Norway	216	Uganda	43	Trinidad & Tobago	18

Country	Sessions	Country	Sessions	Country	Sessions
Uruguay	19	Namibia	6	Liechtenstein	2
Nicaragua	31	Réunion	6	Lesotho	2
Puerto Rico	15	Syria	6	Macedonia (FYROM)	2
Congo - Kinshasa	17	Uzbekistan	7	French Polynesia	2
Laos	14	Bosnia & Herzegovina	5	Chad	2
Belarus	16	Burkina Faso	5	Vanuatu	2
Cuba	16	Bhutan	5	Andorra	1
Cyprus	18	Guadeloupe	6	Angola	1
Iceland	26	Kyrgyzstan	5	Aruba	1
Latvia	13	St. Lucia	5	Bahrain	1
Oman	14	Kosovo	5	Caribbean Netherlands	1
Sudan	13	Antigua & Barbuda	4	Central African Republic	1
Zambia	14	Albania	5	Congo - Brazzaville	1
Malta	13	Barbados	4	Djibouti	1
Mauritius	12	French Guiana	4	Micronesia	1
Togo	11	Guyana	5	Faroe Islands	1
Georgia	11	Haiti	4	Gabon	1
Luxembourg	14	Svalbard & Jan Mayen	7	Guernsey	1
Niger	17	Sierra Leone	4	Guinea	1
Yemen	16	Armenia	3	Guinea-Bissau	1
Afghanistan	18	Gambia	3	Moldova	1
Mali	11	Macau	3	Northern Mariana Islands	1
Dominican Republic	8	New Caledonia	3	Maldives	1
Panama	8	Papua New Guinea	3	São Tomé & Príncipe	1
Paraguay	9	Solomon Islands	4	Swaziland	1
El Salvador	8	Somalia	3	Timor-Leste	1
Palestine	7	South Sudan	3	Tonga	1
Suriname	8	U.S. Virgin Islands	3	Samoa	1
Comoros	7	Azerbaijan	2		
Kuwait	6	Bahamas	2		
Liberia	7	Belize	2		
Libya	6	Grenada	2		
Mozambique	6	St. Kitts & Nevis	2	Total	36754